

Personalised Health Monitoring and Decision Support Based
on Artificial Intelligence and Holistic Health Records

D8.6 - Exploitation plan II

WP8 Communication and Exploitation

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Executive summary

After the first year of the project, this deliverable is reporting on the different activities that are related to the exploitation of the project's results, working to maximise their impact. In that respect, D8.6 – “Exploitation Plan II” is the second iteration of the exploitation plans of the iHelp project and includes the market analysis, target customers and potential business models of the identified exploitable outcomes of the project.

Placing this report in the broader exploitation context, the project is now in the planning stage of the analytical phase. As such, it delivers partners' individual exploitation plans directly linked with their expected results and components, without neglecting the fact that many of these results will be decisive when it comes to the joint exploitation of the project's overall results.

The third iteration of the exploitation plans will be made available on M36 with D8.7 – “Exploitation Plan III”.

1 Introduction

The objectives of this deliverable are to lay out the strategy on how exploitation activities, focusing on the exploitation outcomes, as these have been identified by the Innovation Management activity from T1.3 – “Quality and Risk Management” and the related deliverables.

The document is structured in 13 sections. Further to this introduction, in Section 2 the exploitable outcomes of the project are briefly listed. In the following sections (Sections 3-13), each of these outcomes is analysed in terms of market analysis, target customers and the potential business models. Finally, Section 14 conclude the document and introduces the final iteration of this series of deliverables, i.e., D8.7 – “Exploitation Plan III”.

1.1 Changes since previous version

Contrary to other deliverables of iHelp, this second deliverable for the exploitation plans of iHelp does not build upon the first deliverable, i.e., D8.5 – “Exploitation Plan I”. The older deliverable outlined the exploitation strategy and then detailed the individual exploitation plans of the partners. This deliverable, i.e., D8.6 – “Exploitation Plan II”, provides an in-depth analysis of the exploitation plans for the exploitable items identified in the project.

As such, the two documents are independent, and D8.5 – “Exploitation Plan I” is still relevant after the publication of D8.6 – “Exploitation Plan II”.

2 Exploitable outcomes

2.1 iHelp framework

As healthcare continues to become more complex with more and more data being generated, the industry needs to find effective means of fully collecting, integrating, interpreting, exploiting, and evaluating these large volumes of clinical data. Hence, Healthcare Professionals (HCPs), and administrators in healthcare organizations will be able to make crucial decisions about treatment plans, medications and prevention measures that could improve the treatment and the Quality of Life (QoL) of their patients. Placing healthcare data into the right hands quickly depends on the utilization of Health Information Systems (HIS), which seamlessly and intelligently integrate healthcare with information technology. A HIS enables healthcare organizations to collect, store, manage, and analyse key data of their patients in order to provide data-driven and evidence-based decisions regarding various aspects of patient care. iHelp seeks to introduce such a holistic HIS, as it seeks to deliver a novel personalised healthcare framework focused on the Pancreatic Cancer (PC). This framework enables the collection, integration, and management of health-related data from various sources (medical records, lifestyle, behaviour data, and social media interactions) in a standardised structure, which is called Holistic Health Records (HHRs). On top of this, iHelp introduces a set of innovative multi-level and open-source decision support mechanisms to facilitate the development of personalized risk detection, prevention, and intervention models. iHelp converges techniques from multiple areas, including clinical studies and research on Pancreatic Cancer, Oncology, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Big Data analytics, IoT, software engineering, social media analytics and cloud technologies into a unified software architecture.

Thus, the iHelp outcomes enable the integration of data coming from multiple sources. The iHelp system also provides a way of developing advanced AI techniques that can model the specific conditions of the individual cancer patient, in order to make reliable predictions that can be used in the development of effective patient care plans. Most of its design, the iHelp solution is open by design and fully exploitable, putting emphasis on usability potential integration with different Health Information Systems (HIS) and platforms, thus contributing towards the establishment of a European Platform for Personalised Healthcare.

The most important exploitable result of the iHelp solution is the personalised healthcare provisioning by utilizing integrated data and user-oriented interfaces, prediction, prevention and intervention models, engagement methodologies, and innovative business models, which take into account the user needs and individual preferences. In this respect, the iHelp solution provides enhanced personalized experiences and recommendations based on patient data through different devices and systems. To this end, as introduced in the following subsections, the iHelp project seeks to deliver a set of innovative multi-level and user-centric solutions in the research, healthcare and business communities. These solutions/ mechanisms are listed below:

- AI Models for Personalized Health Prediction,
- Analytic Workbench,
- Big Data Platform,
- Social Media Analyser,
- Monitoring, Alerting and Feedback Component,

- Holistic Health Records,
- Tailored Conversational Coaching System,
- Offline Model Learning System,
- Advanced Notebook,
- Bounce Mitigation

By utilizing the above-mentioned mechanisms and exploitable outcomes, iHelp seeks to acquire and exploit domain knowledge, patient information and new insights into the underlying risks of PC that can be derived from heterogeneous data sources through a holistic data management platform. The latter will facilitate the promotion of scientific advancements and transmission of project results to relevant stakeholders.

2.2 AI Models for Personalized Health Prediction

AI models have been derived for personalized health prediction^{1,2}. These are grouped in two categories:

- **Combination of neural networks trained on static and streaming data:** This outcome concerns the use of streaming data in order to enhance models based on retrospective data. To capture the historical patterns of streaming data, modern neural network techniques are utilized. At the same time, traditional MLPs are trained on the static information. Next, the models are being concatenated into a single classification model using an MLP layer. Since this is about enhancing existing models, it is not targeting any specific societal challenge. It rather facilitates the overall processing and analysis of the data.
- **Constrained clustering to annotate Electronic Health Records (EHR) for Classification:** EHR datasets are present with PC diagnosed and undiagnosed patients. To tackle the task of classifying new patients into groups (e.g., risk level groups) in the case of unlabeled data we propose a constrained k-means clustering technique that forces a clustering which contains all the cases in the same group (e.g., high risk cluster). Other clusters can be interpreted as other categories (e.g., medium, low risk). The resulting clusters can be used as labels for a classification problem. This outcome provides a base technology and techniques to be utilized to enhance the analysis of the data, and therefore, is not targeting any specific societal challenge. It rather provides the stakeholders with much more efficient data analysis, classification, and enrichment.

2.3 Analytics Workbench

The Analytics Workbench has been developed in iHelp to provide a tool/ platform where all the AI/ ML analytical models from the project will be hosted, accessed, and executed. In addition, iHelp users will be given the possibility of training their own models either by using functionalities from the Analytics Workbench or using external analytical tools.

The Analytics Workbench is composed of the following four modules to cover up the different stages of the lifecycle for the AI/ ML analytical models:

- For training an AI/ ML model, non-technical users can make use of the Model Trainer that allows clinicians to train their own models based on a good amount of pre-loaded AI/ML algorithms (injected by ICE AI & Analytics product)

¹ https://www.plattform-lernende-systeme.de/files/Downloads/Publikationen_EN/AG6_4_WP_ES_Business_models_ai_healthcare.pdf

² <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IJEHR-04-2021-0304/full/html>

- For developing an AI/ ML custom model, advanced users such as Clinical Data Scientists, can make use of the Advance Notebook that allows them to develop their custom Python-based analytical models by using Jupyter Notebooks (see section 2.10 for a more detailed definition).
- For uploading and validating AI/ ML models, the Model Manager is responsible for using it in order to close the bridge between design-time components and the execution engine.
- For executing the uploaded AI/ ML models, the Execution Engine is built on top of a Kubernetes-based infrastructure

2.4 Big Data Platform

The Big Data Platform (BDP) is based on LeanXscale datastore with its ultra-scalable database that supports mixed OLAP+OLTP workloads. It allows full ACID transactions to support the flow of insertions and updates of records, while it can also run analytical queries on top of that operational information in real-time. Additionally, it offers multi-datastore support, thus providing polyglot capabilities and enabling the integration with different types of datastores that could be deployed externally to the iHelp platform.

The BDP has the ability to allow for high rated ingestion of health records, ensuring transactional semantics in parallel. At the same time, allows for AI algorithms to perform analytics in real-time as data are being ingested simultaneously, without the need to extract knowledge from a data warehouse that often contains outdated data from a previous point of time (i.e., last day, last week, etc.)

2.5 Social Media Analyser

The Social Media Analyser (SMA) tool has been developed in iHelp to study the societal factors and lifestyle patterns by exploring social media feed. The objective is to create a state-of-the-art mechanism that yield actionable insights that would help the policy makers to improve or create a new and effective policy. It allows the users to create micro-services or applications that can monitor social media platforms for specific topics of interest.

The SMA tool in iHelp will assist policy makers to understand the general perception of social media users regarding healthcare interventions and policies about Pancreatic Cancer. The tool will be able to calculate attributes such as sentiments and polarity, and subjectivity from the social media streams and provide the healthcare policy makers with insight into lifestyle trends, mental models, emotions, social interactions, and societal influences on the individuals.

This would allow policy makers to measure the impact of existing policies and enable them to create robust and effective policies based on public sentiment. With a closer understanding of social media users, policy makers will be able to predict the need for, evaluate, and design policies in order to address and prevent emerging health care needs.

2.6 Monitoring, Alerting and Feedback Component

The Monitoring, Alerting and Feedback component in iHelp has been developed to provide an innovative solution for monitoring remotely the health condition of patients based on the processing and analysis of primary and secondary data collected from wearable and mobile devices.

This component is based on an advanced rule-based engine executed on configurable time intervals (daily, weekly, or monthly) that is performing an assessment of the progress towards reaching personalized

patient targets. In its core functionality, the mechanism will evaluate primary and secondary health data of different patients and will compare certain target values defined in the personalized recommendation against real values. Furthermore, the alerting module will be used to distribute evaluation and feedback messages. Different escalation policies and threshold values will be considered when distributing the proper personalized message to the patient as well as to their clinician.

Moreover, the technical solution as output in T5.5 of the iHelp project allows a flexibility of configurations, context information processing as well as templatization of notifications and can be adopted for remote health monitoring and decision support in the context of other diseases.

2.7 Holistic Health Record

One of the main objectives of the project is to create mechanisms for the realization of integrated Holistic Health Records (HHR)^{3,4,5}. HHR is a structured health-record base that contains interoperable, harmonized, and standardized primary and secondary data that can be enriched with new fields, based on the HL7 FHIR standard. It provides a set of operations on widely used and known medical terminologies used for the coding of medical knowledge, which further enhance the harmonization and standardization of data. One exploitable outcome is that iHelp can contribute to the extension of the FHIR resources via the creation of a Structure Definition resource that is the extension definition. The creation of an extension definition includes the knowledge of in which resource/s extension will go, what datatype/s it can take and what the URL will be. Moreover, since the standardized data are being used for the implementation of the AI models, the outcome of T3.1 – “Data Modelling and Integrated Health Records” is directly connected with the wide use of the outcomes of AI Models for Personalized Health Prediction, even outside the project. (T4.1 – “Personalised Health Modelling and Predictions”).

2.8 Tailored Conversational Coaching System

In T5.3 – “Delivery Mechanisms for Personalized Healthcare and Real-time Feedback”, mechanisms are developed to deliver personalized healthcare and real-time feedback to end-users of the mobile application. These mechanisms include basic functionalities such as showing graphs or other data visualizations or sending messages that are composed by clinicians. The innovation described here focuses on the third mechanism for delivering personalized healthcare: the conversational coaching system. This system consists of (a) a platform for authoring/ defining scripted dialogues that can be executed between user and system and can be personalized using a simple scripting language and an integration with available user data, (b) a user interface developed within the Healthentia⁶ mobile application that allows the end-user to interact with these scripted dialogues, (c) a back-end component that allows external systems (i.e. those that have been provided API-level access) to trigger certain dialogues/ conversations, and (d) an automated system that can decide which topic is the most relevant to discuss for a particular user at a particular moment in time.

³ <https://www.charmhealth.com/blog/ehr-as-business-model-enabler.html>

⁴ <https://acta.tums.ac.ir/index.php/acta/article/view/5790>

⁵ <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/electronic-health-records-EHR-market>

⁶ <https://healthentia.com/>

2.9 Offline Model Learning System

The offline model learning system is a zero-code model learning environment that can be set up in any server. One of the main functions is creating a model learning sandbox oriented towards data scientists working alongside healthcare professionals, or even towards healthcare professionals themselves. Currently it is part of the Healthentia platform ecosystem, a product of our partner Innovation Sprint (INS), but edge versions are also prepared to be deployed in the premises of healthcare organizations to cover the cases where data cannot be ingested into Healthentia.

The zero-code concept is supported via an elaborate experiment configuration system that allows training generative and predictive models employing an ever-expanding portfolio of algorithms. The configuration system proposes reasonable default values to the different tunable parameters, taking into account the expected users, and not requiring the deep knowledge of machine learning engineers.

2.10 Advanced Notebook

This tool is one script deployment for open-source tools that foster faster AI/ ML experiments, based on MLFlow and Jupyter Notebooks. Researchers can interact with the data via web-based notebooks, access the ML models metadata, artifacts, as well as performance indicators via browser. The prediction of the AI can be exposed via REST API using the same notebook, without the need for a different tool. It allows a simple and fast deployment via Docker and allows scalability via Kubernetes. The tool supports any type of AI models, ML Apps, libraries and even the adoption of new classes of ML algorithms. It also supports connection to any database type, and it can load data from different data sources with different formats. It supports languages such as: Python, R, Julia, Scala. In addition, the tool supports model performance monitoring and tracking, including performance degradation monitoring. It offers models management, versioning, and automatic model versioning. It is a flexible framework that can be used for different projects, and in both in-lab or industrial environments and can be easily adapted to different infrastructures and offers scalability properties. Using Docker technologies, the tool can be deployed on premise but also on cloud, supporting deployment on local PCs, virtual machines, or multi-clouds environments including private, public or hybrid clouds. The minimum prerequisites for the simple case, are only a single machine or virtual machine, with resources adapted on the ML experiment. Model Training and Model Prediction can be also separated on different sites and can further support Federated Learning.

2.11 Bounce Mitigation

The Bounce Mitigation sub-component is a script deployment for open-source tools to foster prediction of users that are of risk of quitting the enrolled iHelp health plan and find the reasons behind quitting. The tool is based on the Advanced Notebook utility, where researchers can interact with the data via web-based notebooks. The predicted risk can be exposed via REST API using the same notebook, without the need for a different tool.

Based on existing user actions, activity and interactions with the platform, this tool will analyse the probability that a user will quit the program in the near future and act accordingly to ensure continuity of care. To this scope, for example, an alert will be sent to interested parties (e.g., HCPs) to contact the patient to find the reasons for quitting the current plan and take mitigation actions. The goal is to improve the health of the users, by keeping the patient commitment within the healthcare plan.

The Bounce Mitigation sub-component has two functionalities:

1. the detection if a patient is at risk of cancelling the associated clinical trial by monitoring the user interactions with the iHelp platform and the data following the healthcare plan.
2. to expose, via REST API, this risk as a notification sent to the patient's clinician via the iHelp platform.

The scope of the notification is twofold:

1. for the clinician to gather feedback from the patient about its status related with the clinical study
2. for the patient to raise awareness that clinicians are taking care about their progress within the clinical trial

The tool can easily be adapted to the industry sector to improve the interaction of employers', production line operators with the machines, optimize the efficiency, or even for corporations to predict employment quitting.

3 iHelp framework

3.1 Market analysis

Based on recent surveys, the global HIS market size (see Figure 1) was valued at USD 268.1 billion in 2021 and is expected to reach USD 528.49 billion in 2030 and register a revenue CAGR of 7.8% during the forecast period (2022-2030)⁷. The increased government investments in the development and digitalization of the healthcare infrastructure have significant contributions towards the development of the global HIS market. While the high demand for remote patient monitoring and the development of personal health records are also significantly driving its adoption rate.

Figure 1: HIS market size, 2020-2030 (USD billion)⁸.

To this end, technological advancements in healthcare IT infrastructure, such as the use of IoT, Big Data, and AI are significant factors propelling the market growth. Especially when it comes to the domains of data interoperability, AI, and Machine Learning (ML), several new algorithms and solutions are being widely adopted and integrated into HIS to accurately predict risk of developing diseases in early stages, monitor patients care and provide personalised prevention and intervention measures based on historical and behavioural/lifestyle health datasets. The standardized integration of such data and recalibration of learning models allows the development of AI techniques that provide timely decision support to all stakeholders in the value chain, including HCPs and policy makers using relevant interfaces and Decision Support Systems (DSS). In this respect, recent surveys demonstrate this increasing need of leveraging the capabilities of AI in the healthcare domain as it is also described in section 4 – “AI Models for Personalized Health Prediction”. Moreover, Deep Learning (DL) technologies, predictive analytics, content analytics, and Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools are enabling care professionals to diagnose patients’ underlying health conditions at an earlier stage.

⁷ <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/healthcare-information-systems-market>

⁸ <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/healthcare-information-systems-market>

When it comes to end users' insights, a recent survey indicates that hospitals segment dominated the AI healthcare market in 2021 with a market share of 76.8%⁹. Growing adoption of HIS in hospitals (see Figure 2) has led to increased efficiency of the HCPs resulting in enhanced and personalized patient care. In addition, diagnostic centres are projected to witness the highest CAGR over the forecast period as the adoption and utilization of AI by these centres allows healthcare providers to make informed decisions, which will help in preparing diagnoses or predicting medical conditions like drug interactions and reactions.

Figure 2: Global HIS by end user, 2021¹⁰.

To address the needs of modern stakeholders in the healthcare domain the iHelp seeks to introduce a user-centric and real-world framework following applied research to address the increasing needs on the delivery personalized healthcare based on the AI support for analysing patient reactions and behaviours to prescribed prevention and intervention measures. The HHR and AI-based actionable insights capabilities will be exploited in order to provide QoL-oriented added-value care services for improved QoL. In addition, it should be noted that the project main outcomes (e.g., HHRs, AI analytics, design of personalised recommendations etc), which are further detailed in the below subsections, are validated in 5 high-profile pilots carried out in 5 different countries within and across European Union, i.e., Italy, Spain, Bulgaria, United Kingdom, and Taiwan. The high-risk individuals of these pilot cases are selected to take part in studies focused on early detection of risks and assessment of personalised recommendations.

To emphasize the above-mentioned main outcomes of the iHelp framework, the following SWOT analysis has been prepared (see Table 1):

⁹ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/artificial-intelligence-ai-healthcare-market>

¹⁰ <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/artificial-intelligence-ai-healthcare-market>

Table 1: iHelp framework SWOT analysis

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Novelty of the iHelp approach in terms of its knowledge intensive and personalization features. ▪ Excellent positioning of the consortium in both the AI and healthcare domain. ▪ Strong worldwide exploitation and market update proposition led by exploitation leader. ▪ The solution is based on mature background AI components and technologies of the partners. ▪ Collection, integration, and management of primary and secondary health-related data from various sources in a standardised structure, the HHRs. ▪ Innovative dockerized approach and federated learning implementations. 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Diversity of the partners’ strategic goals, operating domains, and business models. ▪ Lack of established presence in the market of AI-based services for personalised Pancreatic Cancer care, i.e., need for slow start and acquisition of reputation. ▪ Diversity in the products and solutions to be integrated and offered as a single solution-iHelp AI/ML models might need to be reworked prior their upload.
	S	W	
	O	T	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Socio-economic importance of solutions for Pancreatic Cancer. ▪ Sharing of information between healthcare providers and better information management. ▪ Rise of investments in AI-based healthcare solutions, which facilitate access to finance for relevant innovations. ▪ Technology accelerations in the areas of Big Data, AI, personalised healthcare, and emotional intelligence. ▪ Rising demand for evidence-based policies solutions by HCPs and other policy makers. ▪ Improved support for knowledge management and decision making. ▪ Personalized, efficient, and effective healthcare recommendations, preventions, medications, and care plans. 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Lack of adequate datasets for the development and validation of the project’s solutions with a commercialization outlook. ▪ Emergence of competing solutions and services. ▪ Inadequate (or slow) standardization of AI solutions for healthcare (e.g., evolution of the AI as a medical device initiative by FDA¹¹). ▪ End users’ resistance to systems change and implementation. ▪ Compliance in divergent legal and ethical regulations across different organizations and countries.

3.2 Target customers

The target customers of the overall iHelp framework are based on the following four types:

¹¹ <https://healthitanalytics.com/news/fda-outlines-plans-for-medical-devices-with-artificial-intelligence>

1. The Health Care Professionals (HCPs), as personalised healthcare and risk assessment allows HCPs to identify patients who are eligible for appropriate treatments, which results in savings of time and cost. The research, design, and implementation of innovative solutions on personalised healthcare makes diagnostics smarter and more targeted, such in the case of Pancreatic Cancer, where early identification and personalised treatments can help in the design of improved screening programs. The latter will lead to improvements on the monitoring, care and QoL of the patients. The ability to identify which preventative measure and intervention is delivering the desired impact can massively help in the development of new diagnostic and treatment regimes.
2. The Individuals, as health is a very sensitive issue for any individual and the interrelationships between various health conditions make it paramount to raise awareness of risks and relevant interventions. Increased awareness, early risk assessment and personalised interventions can reduce the risks of Pancreatic Cancer, improve health and QoL. Moreover, the direct and (near) real-time communication with HCPs is facilitated through the delivery of user-centric mobile and wearable applications, as also of the DSS.
3. The Data Scientists/developers, as innovative containerized and federated learning approaches will be followed and introduced as SotA approaches to also overcome the ethical and legal issues that may arise by different stakeholders. Moreover, advanced AI-based models for early risk prediction and assessment will be introduced and developed, while a standardized data modelling approach through the realization of HHRs will be followed. The latter leads to the provision of solutions and mechanisms for enhanced information acquisition, interoperability, and aggregation.
4. The Policy Makers, as the use of AI-based analytics (performing cause-effect analysis over the data of individuals from with specific conditions, risks, geographic region, or specific age group) can allow them to analyse the adequacy and impact of specific interventions. The analysis of personalised risks and interventions can also inform the policy making related to design of new and effective screening programs. Moreover, the evaluation and optimization of targeted policies through AI infused analytics/simulations and visualizations can inform evidence-based policy and decision making.

3.3 Potential business models

HIS take care of administrative aspects and patients' medical data, amongst many other things and their adaptation and utilization is of high importance in the modern healthcare and research society. The iHelp platform does not fall out of this trend and, as such, can benefit of the increased revenues prediction by putting in the market its functionalities and targeting the right customers. As such, the following can be potential business models that the iHelp framework can opt for:

- Software as a Service (SaaS) allows a stakeholder to install, manage, and operate software applications, leading to lower operation cost and high provisioning to the end-user. As concerns the iHelp framework, it implies that the service is centralized in a host or set of hosts within the iHelp infrastructure. In iHelp framework such solutions/services can be considered, for instance, the Social Media Analyser and the Monitoring Alerting and Feedback Component, as also mobile services for multi-platform and multi-device support. Moreover, it should be noted that from the early stages of its design the iHelp framework is based on the utilization of authentication and authorization mechanism to guarantee that only authorized users should be able to access the SaaS service.

- Analytics as a Service (AaaS) offering a fully customizable AI analytics and insights solution with end-to-end capabilities, organizing, analysing, and presenting data in a way that lets even HCPs to gain valuable insights and enhance the decision-making processes. The latter will be facilitated through the provision of various mechanisms and components, such as the Analytic Workbench and the Decision Support System (DSS) that will be further analysed in the below subsections.
- Platform as a Service (PaaS) where a fully deployed and ready to be installed iHelp framework can be delivered to a stakeholder. Following a containerized approach by its design the iHelp framework can be installed in stakeholders' servers and premises. The manifests that are developed contain all the needed components required to establish and run the whole iHelp framework.

There could be different possibilities for a stakeholder to adopt the above-mentioned types of services that can be provided by the iHelp framework, and these are only payment, one initial payment, and monthly fees payment depending on the use. The concrete business model that will be followed for the overall iHelp framework, as well as for its internal components and services will be decided during the third year of the project and will be reported in the context of the last deliverable of this series, i.e., D8.7 – “Exploitation plan III.”

4 AI Models for Personalized Health Prediction

4.1 Market analysis

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is defined as an intelligent system that applies several human intelligence-based functions such as reasoning, learning and problem-solving skills in various disciplines such as computer science, mathematics, biology, and engineering. Artificial intelligence in healthcare makes use of algorithms and software to analyse complex medical data to extract useful results not possible before. AI is used within the healthcare sector to research the connection between treatment techniques and patient outcomes. Furthermore, it has several applications in medication management, treatment plans and drug discovery. It is used in medical practices such as diagnostic processes, personalized medicines, drug development and patient monitoring care.

The respective market's growth is mainly guided by the surge in volume of healthcare data and rise in the complexity of these datasets driving the necessity for AI in healthcare. Moreover, improvements in the computing power and decline in hardware costs surge in number of cross-industry partnership, collaborations and rise in imbalance between the health workforce and patients drive the necessity of improvised healthcare services. For instance, in August 2017, Penn Medicine developed a predictive solution using Machine Learning (ML) where the model analysed a patient's vital signs and predicted the risk of developing sepsis and was also able to detect the possibility of heart failure. Nevertheless, the health community is expected to be sceptical due to the risk of injury and misinterpretation and thus limiting the growth of the AI in healthcare market.

Figure 3. Artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare market size worldwide from 2021 to 2030

To be more precise (see Figure 3), in 2021, the artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare market was worth around USD 11 billion worldwide. It was forecast that the global healthcare AI market would be worth

almost USD 188 billion by 2030, increasing at a compound annual growth rate of 37 percent from 2022 to 2030¹².

The AI in healthcare market is segmented on the basis of offering, algorithm, application, end user and region¹³. In the context of T4.1 – “Personalised Health Modelling and Predictions” is also divided into hardware, software, and services (see Figure 4).

Figure 4. Software segment holds a dominant position in 2020 and will continue to maintain the lead over the forecast period.

The software is expected to be the main contributor in the upcoming years due to continuous software innovation satisfying the requirements in healthcare. By algorithm it is classified into deep learning, querying method, natural language processing and context aware processing (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. NLP segment holds the dominant position in 2020 and will continue to maintain the lead over the forecast period.

By end user it is categorized into healthcare providers, pharmaceutical & biotechnology companies, and patients (see Figure 6).

¹² <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1334826/ai-in-healthcare-market-size-worldwide/>

¹³ <https://www.alliedmarketresearch.com/artificial-intelligence-in-healthcare-market>

Figure 6. Healthcare providers segment holds the dominant position in 2020 and will continue to maintain the lead over the forecast period.

Task T4.1 – “Personalised Health Modelling and Predictions” is addressing most of the sectors mentioned above showing that it is in the right path. In particular, it is considered software since the main outcomes are the AI predictive models. Furthermore, in an algorithmic approach T4.1 – “Personalised Health Modelling and Predictions” more or less incorporates techniques and methods taken from each abovementioned segment. Finally, from an end user’s perspective the healthcare providers and the patients are the core entities involved in the produced models.

4.2 Target customers

The next few years, AI-based predictive healthcare networks are expected to improve staff workflow, reduce waiting time for patient management and handling. Furthermore, AI-based surgeries and diagnosis are expected to gain a traction over the forecast period and AI will help to increase the ability of health professionals in order to better understand the needs and daily patterns of the patients. These health professionals can provide better guidance, support, and feedback to patients to stay healthy. The technology on the other hand is significantly improved with the adoption of AI technology in the medicine industry and is expected to fulfil demand for personalized treatment plans for patients administered with precision medicines. Moreover, AI and ML algorithms provides real-time data and analysis which helps medical professionals, clinical experts, and doctors to efficiently identify and prevent the spread of disease at an early stage. It also helps healthcare industry experts to develop precision medicine, drug discovery as well as customize drugs as per individual unique DNA.

To wrap up, virtual assistants, NLP, AI in diagnosis and predictions, drug discovery and development, precision medicine, robot assisted surgeries mental health, wearables are some of the are some of the major trends in the AI in healthcare market. Hence, all the individuals but also the professionals involved in these trends are considered potential customers. Therefore, patients, healthcare professionals, drug discovery healthcare scientists, AI specialists, doctors but also manufacturers of wearable devices are only a few of those considered potential customers.

4.3 Potential business models

Whether in medical services, cancer care or rehabilitation, AI promises huge potential to improve healthcare. New types of innovation processes and innovative business models are needed to enable patients to benefit from this potential. This involves overcoming technical, ethical, regulatory, and

economic challenges. Economically achievable business models assist in bringing AI-based innovations to the center of the healthcare system and urging the digitization necessary for this. In the sequel, an overview is provided of how AI-based business models can be successfully implemented in the healthcare sector in Europe by focusing on opportunities and challenges¹⁴.

AI as an opportunity for healthcare companies

When analyzing the opportunities of AI applications for healthcare companies, it is important to keep in mind that the medical technology industry in Europe is strongly characterized by small and medium-sized enterprises. However, especially for many small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and startups, the financing and approval of AI medical devices in healthcare poses major challenges. Specific challenges include the lack of suitable training data, data security issues, lack of AI expertise, lack of confidence in AI technologies, or the unclear prospect of reimbursement. Pre-financing through the hope of increasing market share also appears risky in some cases. This is especially true for comparatively small companies, as the AI economy is a platform economy dominated by large hyperscalers. For the long-term success of AI-based business models, the prospect of new technology reimbursement as well as specialized funding programs would be helpful.

Nevertheless, AI-based business models offer great potential in both the primary and secondary healthcare markets. The secondary healthcare market is becoming increasingly relevant, which has great potential with meaningful, high-quality AI applications in terms of monetization as well as for personal health and health maintenance. Promising applications for new AI business models for healthcare companies in the secondary healthcare market include personal AI-based health applications such as the evaluation of wearables as well as applications in the field of care and rehabilitation. For healthcare companies, AI applications also offer the opportunity to expand their business models by optimizing existing and developing novel offerings with AI.

AI healthcare applications are based on technologically (complex) AI models and often apply training procedures using numerous clinical data. This costly process must be refinanced via revenue models. The following two revenue models are particularly worthy of mention:

Same revenue model for AI-based improvement of an existing offering

There are applications that can improve, facilitate, and automate an existing offering with AI. AI enhances work and process steps but does not fundamentally change them. Typically, companies use such enhancements to differentiate their products. However, the existing business model – such as the sale of capital goods with maintenance and services – remains unchanged.

Opportunity of new revenue models for novel AI offerings

The situation is different, for example, in the case of decision support systems (e.g., in the pre-classification of radiological image data): Here, the use of AI enables a novel service. To monetize this, different business models can be examined – away from the licensing business with one-off payments to the “software-as-a-service” business, rental model, or usage-dependent payments. At first glance, this benefits the providers of such solutions, because they can forecast revenue much more precisely based on their user numbers over a longer period of time. Users also benefit from such service offerings through reduced costs for the

¹⁴ https://www.plattform-lernende-systeme.de/files/Downloads/Publikationen_EN/AG6_4_WP_ES_Business_models_ai_healthcare.pdf

maintenance and configuration of the software, for example through the automatic provision and updating of the service via the internet or cloud applications. In addition, the expenses for the services, which replace high one-off financing, are spread over the entire term. Very often, the business models are also supplemented by continuous product maintenance and included services such as protection against cyber-attacks and data loss. In this way, customers can also insist on continuous high quality since they are paying continuously.

AI-specific innovation problems: The causality dilemma

One AI-specific innovation problem is the so-called causality dilemma: The quality of the result depends strongly on the quality and the number of data sets, so that the benefit can often only be proven in the long term. Since the proof of benefit is costly, many companies cannot afford the considerable validation effort. To provide an economic incentive, temporary cost coverage should be discussed until the benefit has been proven.

Field of action: Reimbursement and funding

Based on the evaluation of the pathways to reimbursement by the health insurance, it should be discussed whether the existing conditions are already sufficiently tailored to AI-based innovations. Short innovation cycles, the large heterogeneity of applications, and the potential changeability of functionality are just some of the features. It is also unclear whether the existing evaluation processes sufficiently consider the potential of AI. Based on the problem of the causality dilemma, it is apparent that the quality of the technology may increase with more data and training, and thus at the beginning of development the actual benefits may not yet be sufficiently demonstrable.

The secondary healthcare market also offers a lot of potential. Nevertheless, AI-based examination and treatment methods for which the benefit, medical necessity and economic viability have been proven should be integrated into the primary healthcare market. Only in this way all citizens can benefit from holistic, personalized, patient-centered healthcare. This close link between the primary and secondary healthcare markets requires, among other things, a high level of quality assurance in the secondary healthcare market as well.

Field of action: Data

The availability of data, especially training and validation data for AI, is one of the key prerequisites for successful AI business models in healthcare. Much progress has been made in this field of action in recent years, among other things, treatment data are being made usable for research with the help of coordinated patient consents, and possibilities for intersectoral data exchange are being tested. Within the framework of GAIA-X, a European federated data infrastructure is being created in which health data can be evaluated securely and for distributed AI applications across countries in the future. These secure and interoperable possibilities for data storage and data use not only create advantages for individual treatment and patient sovereignty. They also enable new applications at the population level, for example in epidemiological questions.

Field of action: Startup funding and secondary healthcare market

Despite some successful examples of European AI health startups, it is apparent that the funding sums generated are rather low in international comparison. In this context, among other things, the high investment sums and long waiting times present themselves as challenges for SMEs and startups: In the case of digital business models, a lot of money often must be invested in order to build up and establish

platforms. This can be particularly difficult for startups or SMEs. Therefore, from a European perspective, ways should be found to bring AI into the mainstream and make it financeable. The main issue here is to create regulatory framework conditions that make it easier to participate in AI health startups with venture capital/corporate venture capital. It would be important, for example, to make it easier for large institutional investors to invest in startups.

Field of action: Innovation and value creation networks

As in other application fields of digital transformation, the aspect of networking is also of central importance for the healthcare sector. A major added value of digitization in the healthcare sector could be the large number of data points from different sources (multiple devices, different employees, different processes in a value chain), which can be related to each other and thus become the base for a higher level of knowledge. In addition, health status data of a person (holistically or partially) are particularly relevant in the healthcare sector. They can form the base for a digital health twin of a person, which, enriched with information on nutrition, activities, stress, etc., can also enable a simulation of the future state.

Field of action: Certification and liability

When AI is certified as a medical device or diagnostic procedure, it is currently done as standalone software or primarily as part of an overall product. For a medical device to be introduced to the EU market, it must be regulated uniformly throughout the EU, which requires a conformity assessment procedure to prove defined safety, quality, and performance requirements. Depending on the risk class, the respective conformity procedure and the involvement of a notified body differ to independently test and certify the medical device. The European Commission's White Paper on AI points out the danger of unclear regulations on risks, which can lead to legal uncertainty for companies and ultimately reduce their competitiveness. Similarly, users, doctors and patients should not bear the entire risk. For a trained AI system that does not continue to learn during use, there is no significant difference in liability from medical devices. Liability issues could arise in the more distant future with AI systems that continue to learn. This raises the question of whether the liability system needs to be adapted, at least for AI technologies of high-risk classes. Liability for AI systems in healthcare should therefore clearly consider the special characteristics of AI systems, such as errors in the algorithms, or that AI systems can learn based on trial and error or mistakes.

Field of action: Digital ethics and patient perspective

For these AI technologies to establish themselves on the market, acceptance by patients and users is necessary. Important foundations for creating the trust that is essential for the acceptance of AI in healthcare are the establishment of digital ethical principles and their consideration in the development and application of new digital healthcare solutions, as well as the consideration of the patient perspective along the entire digital value chain. This applies to applications that directly affect patients or are used by them. Trust must be promoted and maintained by all players in the healthcare sector, including private-sector market participants. Only in this way there can be long-term acceptance (and success) of these innovations. Trust arises when the technically feasible is measured against legal and ethical standards. This can be achieved through standards, guidelines or "seals of approval," but above all through proven, transparent action. Players in the healthcare sector should proactively and openly commit to taking these principles into account to promote acceptance of and trust in AI-based innovations. To maintain this trust, AI-based business models must always and first be evaluated against the background of the medical benefit as well as against general ethical and social criteria.

5 Model Library

5.1 Market analysis

While the global artificial intelligence market size was valued at USD 93.5 billion in 2021 and is projected to expand at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 38.1% from 2022 to 2030, in Europe the revenues from the AI market are also forecasted to reach nearly USD 15 billion by 2025 (see Figure 7). The statistic shows the size of the European market for artificial intelligence, from 2016 to 2025¹⁵. In 2017, the AI market in Europe is estimated to be worth around USD 580 million. Artificial intelligence technologies are being used in a variety of situations across consumer, enterprise, and government markets.

Figure 7: Revenues from the artificial intelligence market in Europe, from 2016 to 2025

The continuous research and innovation directed by the tech giants are driving the adoption of advanced technologies in industry verticals, such as automotive, healthcare, retail, finance, and manufacturing. However, technology has always been an essential element for these industries, but AI has brought technology to the centre of organizations.

In what iHelp domain is, AI has the potential to transform how healthcare is delivered. Yet we need to understand the impact of AI on the healthcare landscape to pave the way for the adoption of AI solutions at scale. The global AI in healthcare market size was valued at USD 10.4 billion in 2021 is expected to expand at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 38.4% from 2022 to 2030. The growing datasets of patient health-related digital information, increasing demand for personalized medicine, and the rising demand for reducing care expenses are some of the major driving forces of the market growth. The growing global geriatric population, changing lifestyles, rising prevalence of chronic diseases has contributed to the surge in demand for diagnosing and improved understanding of diseases in their initial stages.

Since AI and ML algorithms are being widely adopted and integrated into healthcare systems to accurately predict diseases in their early stage based on historical health datasets, the benefits are many: from early diagnosis to accelerating the development of life-saving treatments, supporting improvements in patient

¹⁵ <https://www.statista.com/statistics/721749/europe-artificial-intelligence-market/>

care, and allowing healthcare professionals to spend more time with patients. At the same time, AI can increase productivity and efficiency of care delivery.

Furthermore, deep learning technologies, predictive analytics, content analytics, and Natural Language Processing (NLP) tools are enabling care professionals to diagnose patients' underlying health conditions at an earlier stage. As an example of the push experimented by the AI technologies and use cases, the Covid-19 pandemic positively influenced the demand for AI technologies and unearthed the potential held by these advanced technologies. Healthcare systems widely adopted these technologies in the rapid diagnosis and detection of different virus strains and utilized personalized information in improving the management of the outbreak. AI/ML algorithms were utilized in the diagnosis sector wherein these technologically driven modules were trained with datasets of chest CT images, symptoms, pathological findings, and exposure history to diagnose Covid-19 positive patients rapidly and accurately.

Moreover, the growing shortage of healthcare workforce drove the adoption of AI/ML technologies. Therefore, AI algorithms can be trained to analyse patient health information which further supports care providers in quickly diagnosing the condition and devising an accurate treatment regime. Supportive government initiatives, the rising number of mergers and acquisitions and technological collaborations, and the ongoing Covid-19 pandemic had a significant role in boosting the growth of the market and accelerating the adoption rate of AI in healthcare. AI/ML algorithms are being widely implemented in rapid and accurate diagnosis of medical conditions after the initial implementation in the detection of Covid-19 positive patients using personalized patient information and data consolidation.

For example, a 2019 study reported in *The Lancet Oncology*¹⁶ has shown the accuracy of an AI system in diagnosing prostate cancer in tissue samples. The system was developed by the team behind the Stockholm3¹⁷ and OncoWatch¹⁸ EU projects. The AI system was comparable with 23 international, leading uropathologists in determining the Gleason score, the most important prognostic marker for prostate cancer.

The Analytics Workbench component that is being developed under iHelp aggregates the different ML/AI models developed during the course of the project and put them in the way for beginning their execution. These models are developed in a way that the analytical needs of the different pilots are covered. The Analytics Workbench, thus, helps the clinician in accessing such models, through the iHelp DSS, so that he can choose the right model for the right patient. As said in the deliverables related to the Analytics Workbench, this component is developed by re-using ICE AI & Analytics product which already accounts with the basic functionality. iHelp contributes to complement this actual basic functionality with the following modules:

- Model Trainer: a design-time module that allows clinicians to train their own models based on a good amount of pre-loaded AI/ML algorithms (injected by ICE AI & Analytics product)
- Advance Notebook: a design-time module that allows clinical Data Scientists to develop their own python-based analytical models by using Jupyter Notebooks

¹⁶ [https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanonc/article/PIIS1470-2045\(19\)30738-7/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lanonc/article/PIIS1470-2045(19)30738-7/fulltext)

¹⁷ <https://eithealth.eu/spotlight-story/stockholm3/>

¹⁸ <https://eithealth.eu/project/oncowatch/>

- Model Manager: a module that closes the bridge between design-time components and the execution engine. Also, by using the Model Manager it is possible to validate and upload AI models developed using external means
- Execution Engine: a runtime module that allows the execution of the uploaded AI models in a k8s-based infrastructure

To emphasize this analysis, the following SWOT analysis has been prepared (see Table 2):

Table 2: Market Library SWOT analysis

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Grants access to any AI/ML model developed within the project ▪ Eases the lifecycle of analytical models, from development to execution ▪ It is an integral part of the iHelp Infrastructure ▪ Empowers users with lower skills to develop their own models 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Non-iHelp AI/ML models might need to be reworked prior their upload ▪ A limited amount of AI/ML algorithms is currently present in the developed version
	S	W	
	O	T	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Clinicians can develop their own models without major skills ▪ Data Scientists can develop their own models by using the Advanced Notebook ▪ The usage of Open-Source products, e.g., MLFlow, can improve the reliability and functionality of some modules of the component 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Strong Open-Source solutions, e.g., Databricks, are a hard competitor to the component

5.2 Target customers

The target customers of the Analytics Workbench as an outcome from iHelp are of three types:

- The clinicians (as model consumer) are the first user of the Analytics Workbench since they will be using/executing the uploaded models to run predictions on patient data
- The clinicians (as model developer) oversee developing their own models by using the Model Trainer module of the Analytics Workbench. This module enables the training of AI/ML models without major analytical skills
- The Data Scientists (as model developer) oversee developing AI/ML models by using the Advanced Notebook module of the Analytics Workbench. As Data Scientists these customers are expected to have great knowledge and analytical skills so they can develop the model that better fit their needs. Alternatively, these users can also develop their analytical models using other tools and upload their trained model to the Analytics Workbench by using the Model Manager

5.3 Potential business models

AI is omnipresent in our everyday lives whether we use mobile devices, wearables, or voice assistants. A new forecast from IDC Worldwide predicts the AI market will have worldwide revenues surpassing USD 300 billion in 2024¹⁹ with a five-year compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 17.1%.

The Analytics Workbench does not fall out of this trend and, as such, can benefit from the increased revenues prediction by putting in the market its functionalities and targeting the right customers. As such, the following can be potential business models that the Analytics Workbench can opt for:

- AI Marketplace where the AI/ML models trained can be monetized as long as they are executed in the iHelp environment. This business model can have two variations:
 - Selling the use of a given model, i.e., licensing it
 - Billing the computer usage for executing a given model
- The *host, harbor and harvest* business model focuses on developing and delivering models without any expensive compute-intensive work. These zero-capital expenses ML models are purpose-built, fast, with scalable computing and a predictable “run cost”.

¹⁹ <https://www.idc.com/getdoc.jsp?containerId=prUS46757920>

6 Big Data Platform

6.1 Market analysis

According to 451 Research market analyst, the global data market is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 10.3% to reach total revenue of USD 146.1 billion in 2022. The greatest growth is expected to come from distributed data-processing frameworks, NoSQL, and NewSQL databases. The fastest-growing sub-segment illustrates the shift toward cloud solutions with a CAGR for DBaaS (database as a service) of 48%. Within the operational database segment, LeanXcale is located in the fast-growing segment of NewSQL, growing at a CAGR of 33%. Even though 31% of clients in 2018 preferred to have their data solutions on-premises, the cloud segment is expected to register the highest CAGR of 62% between 2020-2027.

The market targeted by this innovation is considered mature, as the market is already supplied with many products of the proposed innovation. In terms of targeted verticals, the focus is on the Banking, Financial Services, and Insurance sector (BFSI) segment that had the highest market share in 2020 (30%). Within this vertical, LeanXcale plans to focus initially on medium & large companies without a homologation process, then grow to all large companies. The initial targeted market is the data pipelines acceleration use case. The database market has been split into operational and analytical databases, but there is actually a third category, the data pipeline databases, having this last category account for 70% of the installations. Data pipelines typically use either SQL operational databases, such as Oracle, SQL server or DB2 or open-source databases, like PostgreSQL or MySQL. These pipelines have low data ingestion, slow analytical queries and no scalability and elasticity resulting in slow processes. These are the problems solved by LeanXcale that enable the acceleration of these processes and solves the underlying business problems.

LeanXcale strategic goal for exploitation is to commercialize the customization of its database technology for the finance and insurance market, but not limited to the specific verticals, so the project will enable to perform the large-scale piloting necessary to mature the technology and be able to go to market. The target market is the operational and analytical databases that according 451 Research will reach USD 65 billion by 2020. The financial sector is a sector of USD 731 billion.

Various analyst firms, and others, have coined a multitude of acronyms for to characterize a data management system that its aim is to provide support for Big Data, thus being a Big Data Platform, offering real-time processing capabilities over operational and analytical data. Depending on the unique characteristics and most impressive and advanced functionalities of each of these systems, in cases they do or try to solve the problem of management data efficiently under both analytical and operational workload, these acronyms include, but are not necessarily limited to, HTAP (hybrid transactional analytic processing), Translytics, HOAP (hybrid operational analytic processing) and OLTAP (on-line transactional analytic processing).

Currently, the most obvious trend is that more and more database (and data grid) providers are targeting at least a part of this market. Companies whose products previously only offered operational capabilities, now they try to offer additionally support of data analytics and vice versa. It is not expected that this trend will diminish in the near future. On the contrary, as 5G starts becoming prevalent, the always increasing demand for real-time processing will accelerate even more.

A secondary trend related to this market are the now increased multi-model capabilities, often relying on the support of both JSON documents and graph capabilities; more tuneable consistency; increasing implementation of resource management to support mixed workloads; and more support for both synchronous and asynchronous replication.

Last but not least, the majority of the aforementioned products do or tend support Kafka for streaming data and a number of vendors already do or plan to support Flink. With respect to support for machine learning and AI, Spark is commonplace as is support for Python and R though TensorFlow, surprisingly, is supported by very few vendors. PMML (predictive modelling mark-up language) has growing support but remains a minority interest.

In cases where we have a data management system that can support real-time both operational or transactional with analytic processing, these systems can be divided into different categories: Relational databases, NewSQL databases, NoSQL databases, Graph databases and in memory grids. The most prestigious, market dominant and popular vendors per each of these categories are the following:

- Relational: Actian, MariaDB, MemSQL
- NewSQL: CrateDB, LeanXcale, NuoDB, VoltDB, Esgyn (SQL on Hadoop)
- NoSQL: Aerospike, Couchbase, DataStax, MongoDB, Redis Labs and InterSystems IRIS (pre-NoSQL)
- Graph: ArangoDB, Neo4j, TigerGraph
- Data grids: GigaSpaces, GridGain

The Figure 8 provides a mean for comparison among those vendors. The highest scoring companies are nearest the centre. The analyst then defines a benchmark score for a domain leading company from their overall ratings and all those above that are in the champions' segment. Those that remain are placed in the Innovator or Challenger segments, depending on their innovation score. The exact position in each segment is calculated based on their combined innovation and overall score. It is important to note that colour coded products have been scored relative to other products with the same colour coding.

Figure 8: Market comparison among different database vendors

6.2 Target customers

The BFSI industry must handle vast, diverse data sets which include customer information, product information, solutions and services, financial transactions, buying history, and marketing strategies, among other data. On one hand, there is the need of ingesting high amounts of fast data in real-time. On the other hand, fast analytical queries are needed over this data to find out trends, discover insights, set, or suggest prices, etc. Finally, it is needed to perform analytics (machine learning, data mining, etc.) over all historic data to train models, discover insights, identify trends, etc. These four capabilities today are not found in any single data manager. Ingesting fast data is done today with key-value data stores. Analytical queries are done with data warehouses. Operational data is kept at traditional operational SQL databases.

Our initial target is the Banking & Financial services and Insurance (BFSI) sector. These data-driven companies are looking for solutions to optimize their operations by capturing and analysing a greater variety and volume of data to obtain better business insights. We have gained traction with customers in this particular vertical with contracts attached for CESCE 4th world surety insurance and Informa Dun & Bradstreet, the leader in Credit scoring in Spain, Portugal and Colombia. We just completed a successful PoC with Atradius, the 2nd world surety insurance, through our partner T Systems, and with Mutua Tinerfeña. We started a PoC with Informa Portugal and Axactor in Financial services (multinational, leading in Spain's in debt recovery). We started sales in the cloud with three companies, Inverbis, Catalog Player and Flexicar that will facilitate maturing DBaaS and enable us to sell to the BFSI vertical, the Database as a Service (DBaaS). There are almost 7000 insurance companies, 1500 fintech companies and around 6000 banks in Europe.

According to LinkedIn, the world BFSI sector is 1 million companies split into Insurance 350000, Banking (retail & investment) 200000, and Financial Services 610000. We have identified two market segments we can target based on the number of employees and the size of the IT team: Segment 1: This includes companies with between 50 – 5000 employees and an IT team made up of 10 – 50 people. There are 7500 such companies split Europe (2000), LATAM (770), USA & Canada (2500). Segment 2: This includes companies with more than 5000 employees and an IT team made up of over 50 people. There are 3000 such companies. Our strategy is to initially focus on Segment 1 and use the references to enter Segment 2 that due to their procurement process demands a certain number of references before buying, but they will substantially increase the deal size. For this segment, we are targeting 3 regions that is 1) Spain & LATAM, 2) the UK, Ireland Nordics & Benelux and 3) USA & Canada approached in that order.

LeanXcale has vast potential as it is suitable for any size company/entity looking to manage its data. It is especially suited for data-intensive industries, as LeanXcale is the differential in solving their many pains. Despite initially targeting the BFSI vertical, the telco vertical is equally suitable but has proven harder to penetrate. However, through system integrator CGI, with whom we are to sign a partnership agreement, our database will be used in the largest virtual mobile operator in Spain. We are running a PoC on HPE to use LeanXcale as the NFV Director database to enable them to maintain two of the most relevant worldwide telco customers. Through these references, we expect to achieve sales in this vertical and increase penetration leveraging our system integrator partners such as T Systems, SATEC, and CGI. The European Telco sector is crowded, with 830 operators in 2019, 14x more than Asia and twice those of North America for every billion customers served.

The BFSI companies are data-driven. The efficiency of their business depends on the speed and frequency at which they can perform their business processes. With current technology, the speed and frequency they attain are far from what they need. For instance, our customer CESCE wanted to compute the risk daily based on 3 years of data with the leader database. Unfortunately, the initial load was taking more than two months and the daily load over 24 hours, so the project failed, and they resorted to compute risk in a more inaccurate manner overestimating the needed capital to warrant their insurance operations. With LeanXcale this process was reduced by 257x to 5.5 hours. Now they can compute accurately the risk and improve their profitability by reducing the capital to warrant their operations without overestimating.

6.3 Potential business models

LeanXcale has explored various business models that can be applicable to its product, which will incorporate the advancements developed under the scope of the iHelp project, and more precisely, the activities being undertaken by task T4.4 – “Big Data Platform and Knowledge Management System”. Both Business-to-Customer (B2C) and Business-to-Business (B2B) are being concerned. Firstly, it is important to distinguish what is the meaning of a *customer* for a database vendor.

A data management system is intended to be used by IT services, software applications, or AI algorithms. These services, applications and algorithms have been developed either by software engineers or data scientists and are an integral part of a specific product, exploited by an enterprise organization. This means, that the customer of a database vendor is not an individual end-user, but instead another company.

B2C and B2B models are still both valid in the case of a database vendor with the following difference: we consider a B2C model when a database vendor is directly selling its product to a specific customer, which in our case is another company. This is the case when an organization that develops an IT service or software application decides to make use of the database internally in its product. Therefore, this organization is getting revenue by selling its service or product to individuals and pays a specific fee for using the database. On the other hand, B2B model is also applicable in a database vendor. We can find such scenarios when the database is part of an integrated solution whose target it to be used by other information systems. This is the case of *system integrators* or intermediate organizations that sell their solutions to be part of an integrated platform that belongs to a third party. In such cases, the third parties are using the integrated solution as a product and pays the fee for this use, while the *system integrator* or intermediate organization pays the corresponding amount of many to the database vendor, for using its database.

LeanXcale currently has two distinct ways for selling its product: on cloud or on premise. The Big Data Platform, or LeanXcale database, can be used as a DBaaS using AWS resources. We have developed a cloud console where the customers can login and create their instances, with a specific dimension in terms of infrastructure resources. The following figure (Figure 9) depicts the landing page where the customer can connect and request or manage his or her instances. The costumers can select the region where the database will be actually deployed, in order to cope with possible data constraints (i.e., data cannot be moved outside of the EU). The charge for this service, as it can be found from the official cloud console of LeanXcale depends on the resource dimensioning that the costumer will choose. For instance, for a medium deployment into 1 machine with 16 vCPU and 64 GB RAM, the charge will be USD 1.3824 per hour. For a small deployment into 1 machine with 8 vCPU and 32 GB RAM, recommended for up to around 25GB active data set or 250GB of raw data set, the cost will be USD 0.6912 per hour. For an installation into a cluster of 3 machines, with 2 Datastore Nodes of 16 vCPU and 64 GB RAM and 1 Compute Node of 8 vCPU and 32 GB

RAM, recommended for up to around 130GB active data set or 1.3TB of raw data set, the cost will be USD 3.456 per hour. More info can be found at the LeanXcale's cloud console web page²⁰.

Additional standard charges will be requested according to the data usage of the customer, in terms of storage and network traffic, as follows:

- Database: USD 0.115 per GB pr month
- Backup: USD 0.023 per GB / month
- Network Data Transfer (same region): USD 0.01 per GB
- Network Data Transfer (different region): USD 0.02 per GB
- Network Data Transfer (Internet): USD 0.09 per GB

As it can be noted from the landing page, we offer a discount for using the database for 14 days without charging any fee (see Figure 9).

All customers of LeanXcale using the DBaaS are enjoying a 24/7 customer support and new software updates of minor version (i.e., from 1.9.3 to 1.9.4) are applied automatically by the LeanXcale's technical team along with the required data migration from one version to the other, with no downtime.

Figure 9: LeanXcale cloud console

An alternative model is to install the LeanXcale database on premise of the customer. The benefit of such approach is that the final customer has the full control of his or her data, as data stays on premise and will not leave the organization. That might be crucial in cases where we have sensitive data that cannot be loaded to a cloud provider. In such scenarios, the pricing is a standard annual fee. This fee is being negotiated between the sales department of LeanXcale and the customer.

²⁰ <https://cloud.leanxcale.com/>

7 Social Media Analyser

7.1 Market analysis

The Social Media Analytics size is projected to grow from USD 3.2 billion in 2021 to USD 9.3 billion in 2026, at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 24% during this period. The major factors driving the growth of the SMA are the rising number of social media users, increased focus on the market and competitive intelligence, rising need for social media measurement to enhance the customer experience.²¹

With the growth of digital technologies, people have started using social media for communication, online shopping, sharing moods and news and other social connectivity activities. These have encouraged enterprises to adopt SMA solutions to understand the needs and demands of users. The demand for social media is increasing and so does its market, and it is expected to grow more. This increase is complemented by the increase of the usage of smartphones and the improvement of the different SM platforms leading to an increase of data generated for further analysis. Earlier, SMA was only used by advertisers to market their products. Nowadays, it is also used by large enterprises to create trends and understand the likes or dislikes of their customers or understand the topics which attract maximum attention in real-time. This is also the case for the organizations within the iHelp domain, since the use of the SMA is bound to understand what the global audience is saying about pancreatic cancer and how to change the way this disease is being “advertised”.

Since the importance of public opinion on social media platforms has become prominent in recent years and particularly in the COVID19 pandemic, it has been realized that policy making could be more successful when the policy makers benefit from integrating this publicly available, user-generated data through the technique of social media analytics. Administrations around the world are engaging in initiatives to determine policies based on foresight and forward-looking approaches due to the growing impact of relevant factors from unexplored territories such as social media. As the number of social media platforms and their users grows exponentially the need to address the public sentiment towards any intervention becomes significant. It also adds value to the process of creating a new policy or improving on any existing policy as the information from social media would provide a first-hand account of the public perception about the intervention. As building a policy is a complex process with so many relevant factors intertwined and affecting different aspects of the intervention, the policy makers may welcome new tools and techniques that gather and analyze real-time information based on public sentiments on social media.

The ever-growing popularity of social media has made people somewhat dependent and the public use these platforms to express their sentiments about everything impacting their lives. This generates enormous chunks of ‘big data’ everyday which makes it an asset to explore and analyze. Understanding this data presents opportunities for the policy makers to make informed policy decisions. The conclusions drawn from peoples’ general discussions and opinions help tapping into the collective wisdom of people, that may provide fruitful ideas to approach a problem.

The Social Media Analyzer (SMA) component in the iHelp project is conceived to create a tool based on the above-mentioned assumptions. This tool will help policy makers gather and analyze streams of social media through multiple platforms and draw meaningful information that would help in creating a new policy or

²¹ <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/social-media-analytics-market-96768946.html>

improve on the existing policies. ICE is developing the SMA tool using the approach of “mini-applications” in the context of iHelp.

To emphasize this analysis, the following SWOT analysis has been prepared (see Table 3):

Table 3: Social Media Analyzer SWOT analysis

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Scans social media to get sentiment of public audiences re pancreatic cancer related posts ▪ Allows the creation of microservices (or “mini-applications”) to retrieve specific SM posts ▪ Empowers policy makers to evaluate the penetration of certain messages in the SM users ▪ Combines NLP, Sentiment Analysis and CEP techniques 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ A limited amount of SM portals is supported ▪ A limited types of analysis can be performed
	S	W	
	O	T	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Policy makers from the health domain can develop their own services to scan the SM and derive their own health policies ▪ Usage of a similar approach that has proven successful in other domains ▪ No specialist tool available in healthcare domain 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Commercial solutions, but for other domains, are a hard competitor to the component

7.2 Target customers

The target customers of the Social Media Analytics as an outcome from iHelp are the following:

- Policy makers (as services consumer) are the first user of the Social Media Analytics since they will be using the results of the Sentiment Analysis performed on Social Media data
- Policy makers (as services creators) are in charge of creating their own microservices by using the SMA tool so these microservices can scan the SM to obtain posts and reactions
- Clinicians (as services consumer) will be able to use the Social Media Analytics to understand patients’ behaviour post treatment

7.3 Potential business models

Social Media is omnipresent in our everyday lives whether we use one provider or another, it just depends on the message to be conveyed by the publisher that one network or another is used. As said before, the CAGR until next 2026 is at a pace of 24% reaching USD 9.3 billion by then. It is, thus, of paramount importance to establish business models to better exploit this growing market.

The Social Media Analyzer does not fall out of this trend and, as such, can benefit from the increased revenues prediction by putting in the market its functionalities and targeting the right customers. As such, the following can be potential business models that the Social Media Analyzer can opt for:

- Software as a Service is a revenue model based on a monthly fee, paid through a license. Concerning the SMA tool, it implies that the service is centralized in a host or set of hosts, namely the iHelp Platform. Due to the nature of the clients (hospitals), there will be different hosts to preserve at the maximum the privacy and security of each client. Each of these hosts will contain a version of the application that works with multiple machines, to support scalability
- Deployed solution which is a model based on the deployment of not only the SMA tool but also the entire iHelp Platform to the hospitals' servers. Each of the deployment must contain all the components required to run the platform

8 Monitoring, Alerting and Feedback Component

Health monitoring systems continuously collect health-related data through a variety of sources e.g., medical systems, wearables, mobile devices, and remote patient monitoring systems, to provide feedback on health conditions, disease control and healthy lifestyles. The landscape of health monitoring systems has been considerably enhanced by IoT, mobile and wearable devices that incorporate a variety of sensing mechanisms to be able to provide accurate measurements of health conditions. The remote health monitoring system developed in iHelp will provide an innovative solution to monitoring health conditions based on the processing and analysis of data collected from wearable and mobile devices.

8.1 Market analysis

Personalized healthcare has gained profound importance in the background of the Coronavirus Pandemic. People are increasingly interested in monitoring their health conditions and remote healthcare monitoring solutions have gained attention, as evident by the increased use of wearable devices and smartphones.

The market for Health Monitoring System (HMS) is currently valued at USD 37,115.97 Million and it is expected to register a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 8.97% during 2022-2027 as shown in Table 4. In addition to the Pandemic, the growth in health monitoring systems can also be based on an increase in chronic diseases due to lifestyle changes. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated in 2020 that chronic diseases will account for 73% of all deaths.

The North American health monitoring system market dominated the global market and is expected to show the similar trend in the forecast period. The major factors behind its large market share are an increase in the geriatric population, an increase in chronic diseases and demand for portable and wireless monitoring devices. In Europe, the HMS market is expected to reach USD 76713.85 Million by 2029 as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10. Europe patient monitoring system market by 2029. Source: Data bridge market research and analysis study 2029

The global health monitoring market is competitive and consists of several major players that are at the forefront of implementing new strategies i.e., new product launches, partnerships, and mergers to help them strengthen their market position. The major companies providing industrial scale solutions are Baxter

International Inc., Boston Scientific Corporation, Becton, Dickinson and Company, General Electric Company (GE Healthcare), Abbott Laboratories, Johnson & Johnson etc.

Moreover, niche and more personalized solution providers include MDLIVE, which is a telehealth service based in Spain consisting of board-certified doctors and mental health professionals accessible via phone and video. The company launched patient health monitoring in January 2022 to improve the health of people having chronic conditions. Similarly, Omron (a Japanese company) also launched a heart monitoring device to monitor the risks of heart diseases in 2022 (see Table 4).

Table 4: Scope of the Health Monitoring Devices Market

Market Size	USD 80.75 Billion by 2030
Growth Rate	CAGR of 8.3% From 2021 to 2030
Base Year	2020
Historic Data	2017 to 2020
Forecast Period	2021 to 2030
Segments Covered	Product, End User
Regional Scope	North America, APAC, Europe, Latin America, MEAN, Rest of the World
Companies Mentioned	Abbott Laboratories, Hill-Rom Holdings, Inc., Drägerwerk AG & Co. KGaA, Edwards Lifesciences Corporation, OMRON Corporation, Masimo Corporation, Compumedics Limited, Shenzhen Mindray Bio-Medical Electronics Co., Ltd., Nihon Kohden Corporation, Natus Medical, Medtronic plc (Ireland), Koninklijke Philips N.V., GE Healthcare, Getinge AB, Boston Scientific Corporation, Dexcom, Inc., Nonin, BIOTRONIK, SCHILLER, and BioTelemetry, Inc.

Globally, health monitoring systems are segmented based on the product, end-user, and region. Blood glucose monitoring devices have dominated the market in 2021 based on the product segment. By the end-users, the hospitals held the highest market share in 2021 to cater for effective and early diagnosis of chronic diseases. By region, Asia-Pacific market is expected to grow at the highest CAGR by 2027. However, the trend of personalized healthcare is likely to result in an increase in share of citizens and patients market segment also making an increased use of the health monitoring systems.

8.2 Target customers

Target customers for the health monitoring, alerting, feedback, and evaluation systems include the following:

- **General physicians (GP)** - Health monitoring has evolved rapidly as a doable alternative to traditional healthcare solutions providing timely health condition monitoring and feedback to individuals aiming to maintain their independence. However, owing to the connectivity and data integration supported by the modern health monitoring systems, GPs can remotely track health conditions using the monitoring solution, such as the one developed in the iHelp platform. With this, more data will be available to clinicians which can help with early diagnosis, risk mitigation and personalized treatment plans.
- **Citizens and Patients** - Using personalized health monitoring, alerting and feedback technology, the citizens and patients can avoid time consuming interaction with hospitals and general physicians which in turn reduces pressure on healthcare providers. The health conditions and daily

activities of citizens, patients and dependent individuals can be easily monitored and evaluated by the concerned parties (e.g., healthcare providers) in order to provide feedback and alerts in case of any deviation from expected health parameters.

- **Medical Research Organisations** - Medical research organizations are increasingly interested in data from patients and citizens to be able to conduct research in different areas of healthcare. The use of health monitoring, alerting, feedback, and evaluation solutions can provide vital data to be used in different types of research activities e.g., a large amount of data is needed to understand the impact of lifestyles and behaviors on the occurrence of cancer and cancer related risks.
- **Hospitals** - To ensure timely and efficient health monitoring, alerting and feedback hospitals are increasingly interested in latest technology that can provide access to patient data within security and privacy constraints. The monitoring solution developed in the iHelp project can gather, process, and analyze holistic data before it is made available to hospitals where they can get high-level information about the patients such as the subject's activity and lifestyle changes.

8.3 Potential business models

Different types of business models are used to offer health monitoring solutions in the market. These models range from subscription model, packaged solution model, platform as a service (PaaS) etc. Depending on the nature of the solution, the business models can be tuned according to the different markets such as B2B and B2C.

- **Business-To-Consumer Models (B2C)**
 - The health monitoring, alerting, feedback, and evaluation solution can be offered as a service, which can be made available in the market for customers who are the direct end users of the service. Direct interaction with customers can eliminate the chances of fluctuation in demand and helps to maintain consistency in product development. In this model, the service can be offered under different types of subscription and licensing mechanisms.
- **Business-To-Business Models (B2B):**
 - The health monitoring, alerting, feedback and evaluation solution can be offered to the healthcare providers such as hospitals, medical research organizations, general physicians etc. In such B2B model, the solution can be offered as managed service and platform as a service (PaaS) approach where the solution is maintained by the solution provider and the operational aspects (e.g., user and data management) remains under the control of the user organization. Moreover, the solution can be used by technology companies to foster technical innovations in terms of algorithm improvement and new hardware development.

9 Holistic Health Record

9.1 Market analysis

What we call “Holistic Health Records” (HHRs) in iHelp, is very related to the “Electronic Health Records” (EHRs) that is commonly met in market analyses reports. HHR is an electronic version of patient’s healthcare records, represented in common standards. The global electronic health records market size was valued at USD 30,550 million in 2020 and the predictions appear an increase to USD 63,848 million by 2030. The CAGR is registered as 7.7% in these 10 years. This increase is observed, mainly, due to the major advancements in software technology and in the health sector. Moreover, it is commonly accepted that the increasing interest of AI applications in the development of EHRs software contribute to the market’s grow. Other factor for this increase includes the scientific advancements regarding R&D in cloud storage technology, the increase in geriatric population (since older people are more prone to multiple diseases and there is a need for data storage).

It the Table 5 all the aspects of EHRs (and as a result HHRs) market analysis and customer’s services can be summarized.

Table 5: Holistic Health Record market analysis

Market of Electronic Health Records by:	Details
Product	On-premises Software Cloud-based software
Type	Inpatient Ambulatory
Application	Clinical Administrative Reporting in Healthcare system Healthcare financing Clinical research Computer science research
End User	Hospitals & Clinics Researchers (Clinical & Computer Scientists) Policy Makers
Region	North America Europe Asia-Pacific LAMEA
Key Market Players	Allscripts healthcare solutions Cerner Corporation Computer programs and systems CureMD Corporation eClinicalWorks Other

Depending on the type of relevant applications, the inpatient EHR segment dominated the market in 2020 and there is a prediction for a similar continuation, as it can be seen in Figure 11, bellow.

Figure 11: Positioning of Clinical Application in 2020

9.2 Target customers

The market growth is related to the high acceptance of advanced technologies to meet the growing customer requirements. Integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) to predict EHR-based clinical outcomes has helped shape the patient experience through better care. Growing demand for centralization and streamlining of health administration also drive market growth as it improves the quality of care, resulting in immense patient satisfaction.

EHR vendors are finding some success among smaller hospitals even as many of those hospitals are being bought up by larger systems and forced to integrate onto a single platform. During 2018, 216 acute care hospitals with fewer than 200 beds signed a new EHR contract, accounting for 80% of deals throughout 2017. A plethora of end users and as a result, target customers, can be interested in the evolution of EHRs. The list of the targeted customers includes first of all the hospitals and the clinics towards the development of hospital infrastructure. The creation of advanced storage databases and relevant software in the hospitals' premises could upgrade the procedure of clinical decision making.

Apart from the healthcare provision institutes, the large community of computer scientists and software developers will be extremely interested on having access to well-structured and interoperable databases, from which they could possibly have access to a plethora of anonymized and standardised data. Finally, other interest parties include the decision makers and policy makers.

Finally, and as explained above, HHR in iHelp is based on FHIR standard. The HL7[®] FHIR[®] (Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources) standard defines how healthcare information can be exchanged between different computer systems regardless of how it is stored in those systems. Since FHIR was originally launched, it has been used by healthcare application implementers across the globe, including the payer community. This has led to a large online community supported by web-accessible specifications, community-developed tooling, servers, and libraries. FHIR allows user-defined extensions on resources and data types and the Cloud Healthcare API supports storing and retrieving these extensions. iHelp, via the creation of HHRs can contribute to the extension of the FHIR resources via the creation of a Structure Definition resource that is the extension definition.

9.3 Potential business models

In this chapter one possible business model is described, where HER/HHR can play an extended role in order to support of newer models of care. EHRs must be modified for documenting a clinical process, mainly to support the new business model. Outside of healthcare, information technology has grown by leaps and bounds and is enabling new business models to flourish.

Direct Primary Care: it refers to a practice and payment model where patients/consumers visit their physician or practice directly in the form of periodic meetings for a defined set of primary care services. The EHR plays a major role in not only data collection for analytics, but in providing decision support at the point of care. This is a way to control total costs for the payers while providing quality care. Remote patient monitoring and chronic care management also fall into this category, where patients are taken care of at home and thus decreasing the need for hospitalization or coming to the clinic for a face-to-face visit.

A more solid business model must take into account the SWOT analysis of the implementation of the EHRs/HHRs (see Table 6).

Table 6: EHRs/ HHRs implementations SWOT analysis

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Power management of change in the system ▪ Ability to personalize objects like interface ▪ High availability and support full-time ▪ High accessibility ▪ Security ▪ Technologically modern system ▪ Ease of maintenance & usability ▪ Credibility of the management team ▪ Immediate access to detailed clinical information ▪ Reports customized to meet the needs required ▪ Interoperability ▪ Ability to remotely access the system 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Unavailable system documentation ▪ Graphical interface somewhat confusing ▪ Necessity of paper documentation in some services ▪ Insufficient education and training of health professionals ▪ Limitations of Software and Hardware systems in hospitals
	S	W	
	O	T	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Ability to integrate with other applications ▪ Ability to provide information via Internet ▪ Ability to expand and sustain new services ▪ Increasing importance of digital files ▪ Government incentives ▪ Extinction of paper use in the CHP ▪ Modernization and organizational development 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ High degree of competition from other systems ▪ Expansion of software companies for the health market ▪ Competition / market pressure ▪ Competition for scarce talented IT resources ▪ Economic-financial crisis and subsequent financial constraints ▪ Readiness to recover from disasters ▪ Cyberattacks

10 Tailored Conversational Coaching System

10.1 Market analysis

There are AI systems in operation, attempting to provide coaching services. Lark is an A.I. healthcare provider, servicing patients suffering from or at risk of chronic disease with A.I. Nurses. Those diseases are hypertension and diabetes conditions and also this platform focuses on behavioural health such as anxiety and stress. Lark's A.I. Coaches stay in touch with the program's participants, and they text with them anytime, anywhere, and respond immediately to provide proven outcomes and savings compared to live or telephonic healthcare. Florence is an AI chatbot that works as a personal health assistant for everyone. You can find "Florence Chat" through Messenger, Skype, and Kik. Through this chat you can: Get health information, by asking the chatbot, get rewards and statistics of your everyday activity, subscribe to daily health tips, and find a doctor or a pharmacy. The Buoy is an AI platform that helps people make the best decisions about their health. They interact with users dynamically by providing them solutions based on their criteria. HealthTap assists people who may be sick through the process of getting and feeling well. They use AI to "interview" members, and triage (classify and prioritize) their symptoms. The results from HealthTap AI can be used by themselves or inform one of HealthTap's doctors in a virtual consultation. HealthTap's virtual doctor consultations use text chat, audio-only, or video with audio and text to connect doctors with patients. The doctor provides a treatment plan and the next steps for follow-up. Members can get these services at any time, and in any place. Your.MD is an AI self-assessment tool to create an independent Clinical Advisory Board. The objective of the board is to guide Your.MD's clinical team and safeguard the interests of users. So Your.MD operates at the Pre-primary care stage by giving safe, personalised guidance to anyone who wants to find out more about their health. Healthily is a free self-care app where anyone, anywhere can find safe and personalised information, guidance, and support for their health. This platform assesses, understand, track, and manage user's wellbeing – and find vetted health products and services.

In order to assess how the Tailored Conversational Coaching System (TCCS) is positioned within the broader scope of the market, we have performed a SWOT analysis, comparing the Innovation Potential to potential competitors. When looking at competing products, we have focused our analysis on platforms that allow the creation of custom, natural-language-driven interactive agents. Mainly we have explored various chatbot platforms such as Google DialogFlow or Amazon Lex. These platforms are rapidly gaining in popularity, but ultimately seem to be solutions for a different problem, as can be seen from the SWOT analysis of Table 7.

In summary, the main reason why the TCCS stands out against the competition is that competing platforms provide solutions for a different type of issue, namely that of automating large volumes of service requests that are similar in structure, and that are otherwise handled by low-skilled employees that are following detailed step-by-step instructions. In the case of providing personalized virtual coaching in the eHealth domain, no relevant examples exist, and thus a more "hand-crafted" approach is called for.

Table 7: SWOT analysis for the Tailored Conversational Coaching System

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The TCCS gives full control over the content that is being delivered to the end-user, without “black-box” algorithms or tools that provide an obscured natural language generation step. ▪ The TCCS allows customers (i.e., healthcare organisations) to bring their own flavour into the conversations that the virtual agents can have with their customers (e.g., patients). 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ There is a significant time investment needed in creating customized, hand-crafted conversations that make up the bulk of the coaching content. ▪ The solution is still at an R&D level of implementation, meaning that there is still a significant amount of work to be done in order for it to become a marketable solution at scale.
	S	W	
	O	T	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Whereas many competing platforms originate from the customer service field (and then aim to transition into healthcare scenarios), the TCCS has been designed and built from the ground up to be used in healthcare. ▪ The TCCS, and the development thereof, is based on many years of R&D research within the Horizon 2020 framework and has seen various applications throughout its lifespan. ▪ Therefore, we should have a higher level of trust when approaching potential clients from this same healthcare domain. 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Many large tech companies are involved in the field of chatbots and dialogue platforms. Although they still seem to be focused on solving a different problem (that of providing a natural language user interface to a troubleshooting problem within a specific domain, with the ultimate aim of replacing human call-centre operators), these tech companies may one day pivot and focus on providing high-quality healthcare coaching interactions. When they do, they have the power and capital to rapidly overtake smaller players.

10.2 Target customers

The end-users of the Tailored Conversational Coaching Systems are either patients (in a clinical context), or citizens (in a prevention context) who will receive personalized coaching on their routine behaviours. However, from a business perspective, these end-users are not the target customers for the solution on offer. Instead, it is the organisations that offer the treatment or prevention programme to their end-users that are the primary target customers for this Innovation Potential.

Thus, broadly speaking, the target customers for the Tailored Conversational Coaching Systems are *Healthcare Organisations* that can operate and deploy a treatment or prevention programme to end-users. More specifically, we can distinguish e.g., the following cases:

- Small healthcare practices for e.g., Physiotherapists, or General Practitioners that want to offer a premium digital service to their clients.
- Larger scale healthcare organisation, such as Hospitals and rehabilitation centres that want to offer digital services to their range of clientele.
- Public health-related organisations such as Health Insurance Companies that want to offer e.g., prevention-oriented digital support services to their clients.

10.3 Potential business models

As a business model, we aim to target those organizations mentioned above that want to create, build, or configure a Digital Therapeutics (DTx) application that coaches patients through a therapy enabling self-management of a disease. From the client's perspective, the solution should be highly personalized to the end-user and the virtual coach should be "flavored" according to the client's organizational profile.

To those clients, we aim to offer a platform-as-a-service or software-as-a-service approach and together with the client create a custom solution for their needs.

Revenue can be generated through consultancy activities (e.g., assisting in developing the client-custom solution), and through subscription services of the software.

11 Offline Model Learning System

11.1 Market analysis

The competition to the offline model learning system is the zero-code, low-code, or full code sandboxes in the market.

The zero-code competition is as follows: Teachable Machine²² is only applicable in building image- and sound-based models. Following their claim, it allows you to “train a computer to recognize your own images, sounds, & poses”. Knime²³ is an open-source Analytics Platform with visual interface that “lets you build analyses of any complexity level - from automating spreadsheets to ETL to machine learning. Users can access, blend, analyze, and visualize data, without any coding, or integrate their favorite tools and libraries as needed.” SAS Viya on AI Solutions²⁴ provides “comprehensive, intuitive machine learning tools with automated feature engineering, providing you with intelligent recommendations for faster, smarter decision making.” TAZI AI²⁵ claims to bring “an easy-to-use AI/ML to the hands of the domain experts, empowering them to make better decisions based on objectives, solid and constantly updated predictions.” Forecast Pro²⁶ is a forecasting software that creates statistically based forecasts and machine learning models. In particular, Forecast Pro uses Extreme Gradient Boosting Decision Trees and includes a predefined set of features allowing you to build models.

The low-code competition mainly comes from ClearML²⁷, claiming to “turn your experiments into MLOps with only 2-lines-of-code,” following an approach to “easily develop, orchestrate, and automate ML workflows at scale.”

There are full-code online platforms allowing training models, like Google Colab, Kaggle Kernel, Jupyter Notebook on GCP, Amazon SageMaker or Azure Notebooks. Each of these platforms allow some graphical configuration, e.g., on the use of GPUs or TPUs, but beyond that, they depend on your programming skills for learning the models, involving e.g., Tensorflow or Scikit-learn. There are alternatives built by EU co-funded projects, like the INFINITECH testbed, or the COVID-X one. In these testbeds there are some systems already in operation that can help in certain processes, like anonymization engines. The competition analysis follows in the form of a SWOT analysis of the proposed offline model learning system shown in Table 8.

11.2 Target customers

The target customers of the offline model learning system are healthcare organizations with data warehouses and the data science department maintaining them.

²²<https://teachablemachine.withgoogle.com/>

²³<https://www.knime.com/>

²⁴https://www.sas.com/en_gb/software/viya.html

²⁵<https://www.tazi.ai>

²⁶<https://www.forecastpro.com>

²⁷<https://clear.ml/>

Table 8: SWOT analysis for the Offline Model Learning System

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Allow the healthcare professionals to enter the field of model creation following a zero-code approach. ▪ Models with focus on healthcare industry, smart enough to handle issues in datasets in the domain. ▪ Both predictive and generative model learning is covered. ▪ Data pre-processing options can easily be switched in and configured: Attribute selection and combination, definition of input attributes and outcomes, imputation strategies and quantization are some of the options made available via the UI. ▪ The graphical configuration with reasonable defaults explains the process all the way and facilitates repetition of the model learning experiments with small variations or on new data. 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The supported algorithms allowing full configuration via the UI is slowly expanding.
	S	W	
	O	T	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Personalised medicine needs models and AI sorting out the simple cases and allowing the professionals to focus where they are actually needed. Healthcare organizations with access to data can allow the medical personnel to experiment with model learning. ▪ Most of Zero-code competitors are focused on general purpose ML algorithms. ▪ Competitors that provide services for healthcare industry support only basic ML algorithms. 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Not healthcare professional-friendly configuration, difficult to use by all healthcare professionals without some help from data scientists or ML engineers.

11.3 Potential business models

There are two different business models for the offline model learning system:

- It can be used as another Healthentia platform service, following the Healthentia SaaS model. User accounts with the right to use the system will have some elevated fee. The service has access to the Healthentia behavioural data, and any clinical data the healthcare organization has allowed to be ingested in Healthentia.
- It can be used as an edge service, purchased by healthcare organizations, and installed in their premises for use with clinical data they own. Access to Healthentia behavioural data, via the use of the Healthentia API, is important if the organization is also using Healthentia for real-world data collection. In that case access can be provided at some elevated Healthentia SaaS fee.

12 Advanced Notebook

Exploitable strategy and assets

The strategy and plan set out below defines the successful exploitation of the project results. The overall strategy focuses on defining:

- (a) the results that can be exploited,
- (b) market analysis,
- (c) target users, and
- (d) a preliminary business model.

Exploitable result: Proposed method of exploitation

We will identify a suitable manager for the tool, either from within the consortium or the regional networks who will host the tool and make it available beyond the project.

The Advanced Notebook methodology will serve as a basis for further research in the field of impact assessment. The methodology and the related set of variables and indicators developed in WP4 will remain public documents and datasets and available as complementary information to the iHelp.

Policy recommendations for the prioritisation of ML modelling investments in AI application developments will be produced to condense the experience and outcomes of the project.

12.1 Market analysis

Market definition: Technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), and the internet of things (IoT) are currently being used and needed more and more in different industries, fact which accelerates the use of platforms and software and at the same time the expansion increases the data volumes daily. One such piece of software that is currently being used extensively by industries is the data science platform. This programme is made up of several different technologies for machine learning and advanced analytics. It gives data scientists the ability to create methods, draw conclusions from data, and share those experiences. While due to the increase in data volumes, modern data handling systems and data modelling processes are also required in data science initiatives.

The data science and machine learning (DSML) platform market comprise coherently integrated products, components, libraries, and frameworks (including proprietary, partner-sourced and open-source) supporting the entire life cycle of a data science project (e.g., data exploration, model development, and model distribution). It facilitates data preparation and data visualization while providing a large-scale computing infrastructure²⁸.

Size and growth: In 2021, the data science platforms market size was estimated at approximately USD 96 billion, and it is expected to hit around USD 378 billion by 2030, poised to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of more than 16% over the forecast period 2022 to 2030^{29,30}.

Trends: Customers continue to produce massive amounts of structured and unstructured data through mobile applications and other handy solutions. Industry players are actively introducing new cloud-based

²⁸ <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/data-science-platforms-market>

²⁹ <https://www.gartner.com/reviews/market/data-science-and-machine-learning-platforms>

³⁰ <https://www.marketsandmarkets.com/Market-Reports/data-science-platform-market-21532997.html>

data science platforms with advanced features and capabilities. Firms going through digital transformation no longer consider data science platforms as an optional expenditure since they are recognizing that data science platforms allow organizations to make better informed decisions based on real scenarios and accurately predict probable future outcomes.

The technological trends in this sector for features/concepts being implemented in solutions potentially competing in the market with the Innovation Item, refer to: data sharing properties, multi-cloud deployment, models sharing, automatic model versioning, performance degradation, models explainability and root-cause analysis, ML alerts and notifications, and many more.

Market segment: It relates to healthcare applications that help prevent cancer and industrial AI applications.

Competitor analysis: Competitors in the DSML market will be analysed to get a better understanding of the market and how competitive it is. This is a critical element in creating a successful exploitation plan.

The principal competition to the Advanced Notebook is: TensorFlow Serving which works only with TensorFlow models, Kubeflow but has a steep learning curve, BentoML which does not scale out of the box, Sagemaker that works only with AWS and Vertex AI which runs only on the Google Cloud Infrastructure. Each of these platforms provide functionalities like Advanced Notebook, but they are either not open-source or do not have all the functionalities of model deployment or model management.

- TensorFlow Serving - Works only with TensorFlow models
- Kubeflow - learning curve too steep
- Cortex - The setup process can be extremely hard
- Seldon – it is not free, and the setup can be difficult
- BentoML - does not scale out of the box
- Sagemaker - works only with AWS
- Vertex AI (Google Cloud AI Platform) - runs only on the Google Cloud Infrastructure
- H2O.ai - not open source
- Clodedloop.ai - not open source

The SWOT analysis is given in Table 9.

12.2 Target customers

The tool can be applied to any market and is easily transferable to what is most convenient. The main stakeholders could be within the healthcare domain, such as hospital researchers, clinical professionals, medical centres, hospital managers, scientists, medical device manufacturers, medical IT personnel; or within the industry actors (i.e., companies), EU & national wide policy and standardization bodies, education & research organizations like research centres, universities and local authorities like municipalities or regional administrations.

In the next version of this deliverable, more information will be provided on:

Customer Segment - identify who has potentially use for the proposed solution, define target customers in more detail. Establish and detail the profile of the customers, the industry in which they are operating in, as well as connecting them to the problem in question.

Early Adopters - find a small niche that is having the biggest use for this tool, the ones that need ‘early adopters’ the most. These will be the first customers of the proposed solution and will be connected to the problem, it will be explained exactly why these will be the first adopters, and the current connection to them will be clarified.

Table 9: SWOT analysis for the Advanced Notebook

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ A strength of the Advanced Notebook is related to the mature background AI components and technologies. ▪ It offers fast prototyping and easy deployment ▪ Offers flexible framework, be easily adapted to different infrastructures, offers scalability properties, can be deployed in private environments but also on cloud (multi-cloud). ▪ Model Training and Model Prediction can be also separated on different sites and can further support Federated Learning. ▪ Offers models management, versioning, and automatic model versioning ▪ Supports big data processing but also small data sources equally well ▪ Can be adapted to other segments of the market such as industrial applications ▪ Offers model performance tracking, metadata access, performance indicators via browser ▪ Provide Insights into model XAI (Explainable AI) to offer better understanding of model functioning 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ It requires some effort to configure the solution ▪ It requires managing infrastructure in this form, but can be adapted to be deployed on a public platform with automated management
	S	W	
	O	T	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The Advanced Notebook can be connected to various repositories and can be easily integrated to almost any application and use case 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ In a healthcare context, is not so easily to be configured by clinicians only, so it can be difficult to use by all healthcare professionals without some help from data scientists, ML engineers or hospital IT managers.

12.3 Potential business models

This application can be used either integrated in iHelp platform connected to LXS database or completely independent connected to several types of repositories, performing analysis upon request. This makes the solution useful in niche cases where the need for data transforming or custom modelling is not necessarily needed.

The solution is provided as an open source, so it can be extended by other users free of additional costs.

13 Bounce Mitigation

Exploitable strategy and assets

The strategy and plan set out below defines the successful exploitation of the project results. The overall strategy focuses on defining:

- (a) the results that can be exploited,
- (b) market analysis,
- (c) target users, and
- (d) a preliminary business plan

This plan builds on the initial exploitation plan which has been defined by the partners in the project proposal and is based on how to successfully exploit the innovation, in this case Bounce Mitigation and the accompanying research that will arise from the iHelp project. A dedicated exploitation of the iHelp innovations will ensure the results are used beyond the project's duration.

The results that can be exploited

The bounce mitigation can be used to optimize the prevention of users leaving the iHelp system and quitting the established healthcare plan.

Engaging as many people as possible in this program helps gather more data. The more various data is, the more versatile the prediction models are:

- 1 - initially, data relevant to user engagement must be analyzed: correlations between factors must be indicated
- 2 - once correlations have been found, a mathematical model can be designed to predict when and why a user will quit the system

13.1 Market analysis

Market definition: A unique perspective is emerging, namely, that customers can cocreate value, cocreate competitive strategy, collaborate in the companies' innovation process, and become endogenous to the firm. Central in this new view is the concept of customer engagement, defined as the behavioural manifestation from a customer toward a brand or a firm which goes beyond purchase behaviour (N., S., P., 20) (B., L., B., + 10) (VD., L., M., + 10).

Size and growth: The global Customer engagement solutions market size is expected to grow from USD 19.3 billion in 2022 to USD 32.2 billion by 2027, at a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 10.8%³¹.

Trends: Unlike the recessions in the past where the shift was due to the markets, the pandemic has changed consumer behaviour in diverse ways. It is these changing preferences that are driving a change in business strategy.

³¹ <https://www.globenewswire.com/news-release/2022/05/20/2447591/0/en/The-global-Customer-engagement-solutions-market-size-is-expected-to-grow-from-USD-19-3-billion-in-2022-to-USD-32-2-billion-by-2027-at-a-Compound-Annual-Growth-Rate-CAGR-of-10-8.html>

For example, click-and-collect sales in the United States alone grew by 60% for over-the-counter medicine, groceries, household supplies, and personal care products. 75% of U.S. consumers are trying new shopping behavior in response to economic pressures, store closings, and changing priorities and most intend to continue it beyond the crisis.

Market segment: It relates to applications that help preventing user quitting the enrolled healthcare plan.

Every year health plans and providers spend a lot of time, resources, and cash fighting to retain their members. There are conferences specifically focused on member engagement and retention, allowing organizations to learn tips and tricks from industry leaders.

One strategy for member retention is asking the question “who is likely to disenroll from my plan”. Predicting member disenrollment (“churn”) is an extremely common use case in any member population in which plan choice is an individual’s decision.

Retaining 100% of members year after year is unrealistic, but the disenrollment rate would worth even reducing from 10% to 9%. That 1% difference in the targeted population makes a difference not only financially saving, but also improving the quality of life of those individuals. With 1% having such a significant impact, is reasonable for health plans and providers to look for solutions to identify which members are to disenroll from their plan. Members that are identified as “high-risk” can be enrolled into incentive/intervention programs in hopes to change the predicted outcome.

The technological trends in this market regarding features refer to: behaviour users monitoring, churn prediction, targeted user retention, user activity reports, personalized alerts & notifications, models explainability.

Competitor analysis: The existing competitors either do not provide open sources available for large use or they offer paid licensing (i.e., ClosedLoop.ai) or they are not adopted for clinical studies retention but only for healthcare vital signs monitoring apps.

Imi-paradigm (<https://imi-paradigm.eu/petoolbox/monitoring-evaluation/>), H2O.ai (<https://h2o.ai/>), ClosedLoop.ai (<https://www.closedloop.ai/>), Aporia (<https://www.aporia.com/>), Square Customer Engagement (<https://squareup.com/us/en/customer-engagement>), IBM Customer Experience Analytics (<https://www.ibm.com/watson/customer-engagement/resources/customer-experience-analytics/desktop/index.html>), Sumo (<https://sumo.com/stories/guide-to-using-heat-maps>), Hubspot (<https://www.hubspot.com/products/marketing/analytics>), Userlane (<https://www.userlane.com/>), Crystal (<https://www.sap.com/products/technology-platform/crystal-bi.html>), Intercom (<https://www.intercom.com/customer-engagement>) - not open source.

The SWOT analysis is shown in Table 10.

13.2 Target customers

Hospitals, medical centres, hospital managers, scientists, medical device manufacturers, medical IT personnel; industry actors (i.e., companies), education & research organizations like research centres, universities and local authorities like municipalities or regional administrations.

The targeted users are the participants to this platform:

1. the patients, who are the main beneficiaries of iHelp
2. clinicians, who can coach the patients if reasons appear for the later to leave the system
3. policy makers who can create different policies to help user engagement in this program

Table 10: SWOT analysis for the Bounce Mitigation

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Our contributing factor technology unpacks the “black-box” of artificial intelligence, allowing clinicians and care managers to understand the factors (reasons) behind a patient’s risk score of quitting the enrolled healthcare plan. Organizations can group similar cohorts together and enrol patients into individualized interventions they will benefit most from 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Development time can be costly and its unpredictable and depends on existing data
	S	W	
	O	T	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The data that can be used to predict the iHelp clinical study dropout can relate not only to the User Engagement data, but also to the healthcare plan related data: like clinical questionnaires and actions taken by the patients when pursuing the healthcare plan 			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Data for building such tool may prove to be irrelevant

13.3 Potential business models

Potential directions to follow can start from the following:

- reinforce partnership with users by getting feedback using forms
- use the current experience to analyze weak spots of the applications
- inform the users about next/current improvements to the platform that could help their engagement

14 Conclusion

Deliverable D8.6 – “Exploitation Plan II” is the second iteration of the exploration plans, and it will be followed by one more iteration with deliverable and D8.7 – “Exploitation Plan III” (M36). The overall exploitation strategy of the project follows a 3 phases-approach and is described with a list of key tasks, considerations and IPR handling practices. In its second year, the project has finished the second of the three phases, the analytical phase, in which the Innovation Management activity (T1.3) that is linked with WP8 exploitation activity (T8.2), is capturing and monitoring the exploitation potentials of the project. To this end, this report provides in-depth analysis of the exploitation plans for the exploitable items identified in the project. Concerning the joint exploitation, the project foresees the overall iHelp solution to be the main result and the basis for joint exploitation and has considered from this early-stage important parameters that will be help the smooth exploitation. Finally, the document includes the individual market analysis, exploitable strategies and potential business models for the iHelp platform as a whole, but also for the individual exploitable items and components that have been identified by the partners, describing their intentions for exploitation of iHelp outcomes.

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List of Acronyms

AaaS	Analytics as a Service
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BDP	Big Data Platform
CAGR	Compound Annual Growth Rate
DL	Deep Learning
DTx	Digital Therapeutics
EHR	Electronic Health Records
EHR	Electronic Health Record
HCPs	Healthcare Professionals
HHR	Holistic Health Record
HIS	Health Information Systems
HIS	Health Information Systems
IoT	Internet of Things
iSPRINT	Innovation Sprint
ML	Machine Learning
MLP	Multi-Layer Perceptron
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OLAP	OnLine Analytical Processing
OLTP	OnLine Transaction Processing
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PC	Pancreatic Cancer
QoL	Quality of Life QoL
SaaS	Software as a Service
SIE	Siemens
SMA	Social Media Analyser
TCCS	Tailored Conversational Coaching System